

Proceedings: National Watershed Water Quality Project Symposium

FOREWORD

The lessons learned from watershed projects addressing nonpoint source problems are recorded in these proceedings of the National Watershed Water Quality Project Symposium, held September 22-26, 1997, in Washington, DC. The Symposium was conducted by the: U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, U.S. Department of Agriculture; Cooperative State Research Education & Extension Service, Natural Resources Conservation Service, *Maryland Department of Natural Resources*, and Conservation Technology Information Center (CTIC). The Symposium featured accomplishments of local projects funded under EPA's Section 319 (Clean Water Act) National Monitoring Program and USDA's Demonstration, Hydrologic Unit Area Programs, and Management Systems Evaluation Areas. The symposium also featured lessons learned in the Farm*A*Syst and Home*A*Syst programs.

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The success of the symposium and the information transferred from it and the proceedings is due to the expertise and efforts of many individuals. The sum of these are greater than the each individual part and will hopefully be multiplied many times.

Authors

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Peer Review

Numerous individuals were involved in the peer review process, too numerous to list, but their invaluable insights and comments *improved* the scope and direction of each of the papers that they reviewed.

Program Committee

Appreciation goes out to those individuals on the committee that represented their organizations in planning the program. Their tireless efforts provided insight to the agenda and the tours.

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Twenty Years of Change: The Lake Erie Agricultural Systems for Environmental Quality (LEASEQ) Project

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Concern over the “impending death” of Lake Erie in the early 1970’s led not only to extensive point-source improvements but to some of the earliest and largest-scale efforts to implement agricultural best-management practices in the United States. Between 1975 and 1995, a number of implementation, education, and demonstration projects were carried out. While all were in response to the general goal of reducing pollutant export into Lake Erie, they were run by different managers responsible to different agencies. In a sense, this has been an experiment to see if environmental progress can flow from a mosaic of loosely-integrated programs in which participation is largely voluntary.

Figure 1. The Lake Erie drainage basin, showing the location of the study watersheds

The Lake Erie basin has also been the site of an ongoing monitoring program of unusual detail, carried out by the Water Quality Laboratory at Heidelberg College (HCWQL), which has produced daily and more frequent observations of sediment and nutrient concentrations in the

Maumee River at Bowling Green and the Sandusky River at Fremont beginning in 1975. These datasets now contain in excess of 8500 records each, and represent a valuable resource for evaluating the water quality benefits of changing agricultural management practices.

LEASEQ is a USDA-funded retrospective evaluation of changes in land management, soil fertility, farm economics, and water quality in the Maumee and Sandusky River basins of the Lake Erie watershed in the 21-year period between 1975 and 1995. Due to space constraints, this paper will report findings for the Maumee River basin only; results for the Sandusky are similar in most respects.

Environmental Management

Changes in Point Sources

Early efforts to reduce eutrophication in Lake Erie focused on upgrading sewage treatment plants in the Lake Erie watershed; these improvements were well underway by the beginning of the study period. As a result, and because of the relatively small populations served by sewage treatment plants located upstream of the monitoring stations, point sources are relatively minor components of annual nutrient loads, as shown for phosphorus in Figure 2. Point source data for nitrogen are not available, but our estimates indicate that point sources contribute an even smaller portion of the total nitrogen loads than they do for phosphorus, even with the nitrification of ammonia.

Figure 2. Total annual loads of phosphorus in the Maumee River, divided into point and non-point components

Changes in Agricultural Land Use

Agriculture is the dominant land use in the Maumee basin: in 1995, 88% of the land area was farmland, and 76% of the basin was in crop production. During the study period, the number of farms has decreased but the average farm size has increased. The total acreage of farm land has remained about the same (Figure 3). The major crops in the basin are corn, soybeans, and wheat. In 1995, 35% of the Maumee watershed was in soybeans, 23% in corn, 13% in wheat, 6% in other crops, and 12% in non-crop agricultural land use. During the study period, the number of acres in corn and in wheat has decreased by about 20%, while the number of acres in soybeans has increased by about 12%, as shown in Figure 4.

During the study period, implementation of no-till and reduced-till farming has increased substantially (Figure 5), from less than 5% to more than 50%, although data are not available for the early part of the period. The greatest increases have occurred in the last five years, and are due to no-till soybeans. Successful no-till corn farming is more challenging, and implementation percentages have plateaued or decreased slightly in recent years.

Figure 3. Farm land use in the Maumee Basin, 1975-1995

Figure 4. Trends in cropping patterns in the Maumee Basin, 1975-1995

Figure 5. Conservation tillage adoption in northwest Ohio, 1975-1995

Sales of fertilizer phosphorus peaked about 1980 and have since declined by nearly 50%. Sales of fertilizer nitrogen peaked in the Maumee basin about 1980 and have since decreased by about 25% (Figure 6). Phosphorus from manure constitutes 15% to 20% of that from commercial fertilizer, and nitrogen from manure constitutes 30% to 40% of that from commercial fertilizer. Both have declined about 20% over the 20 year study pattern, primarily since the early 1980's.

Figure 6. Commercial fertilizer sales in the Maumee Basin, 1971-1995

Changes in the Soil Resource

Unit area loads of sediment, phosphorus and nitrogen (nitrate plus Kjeldahl) monitored at the Maumee River sampling station at Bowling Green, Ohio, average 614, 1.2, and 19.9 lb/acre/yr, respectively. Over the 21-year study period, these losses amount to more than 26,000,000 tons of sediment and 50,000 tons of phosphorus, and nearly 850,000 tons of nitrogen for the watershed as a whole. Since point sources are a minor component of loads, and 88% of the basin is in agricultural land uses, most of these loads represent losses of resources from agricultural lands.

Comparisons of soil cores from the 1950's and 1960's, archived at Ohio State University, with cores from the same locations taken in the past year, indicate that soil fertility has generally increased during the study period, in spite of losses to erosion. Phosphorus levels are generally above those required for crop maintenance, and are believed to still be increasing gradually. However, nutrient use has become much more efficient. Watershed-wide mass balance calculations indicate that, in the peak three years of the study period, 1979-1981, about half of the phosphorus coming into the watershed from all sources was not exported, but contributed to nutrient buildup. In the final three years of the study, the phosphorus surplus was down to five percent, a very significant improvement in the efficiency of nutrient use.

Change in Crop Yields

Crop yields for the three major crops, measured on a per-acre basis, have increased during the study period (Figure 7). Corn yields are up about 25%, wheat 30%, and soybeans 17%.

Figure 7. Crop yields in the Maumee Basin, 1975-1995

Changes in Water Quality

Water quality changes were evaluated by conducting trend studies of concentrations and loads. Trend analyses were performed on load and concentration data aggregated at the daily, monthly, and annual levels as well as on storm event loads and concentrations. Most analyses were done using log-transformed concentrations or loads, using an ANCOVA model which included the month (categorical variate) and the log of flow (continuous) as well as time (continuous).

The results of representative trend analyses are shown in Figure 8 for discharge, suspended sediment (SS), total phosphorus (TP), soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP), nitrate + nitrite (NO₃), and total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN). Within each group of bars, the leftmost is the trend based on annual loads, the next is annual flow-weighted mean concentrations (FWMCs), the third is storm event mean concentrations (SEMCs), the fourth is monthly FWMCs, and the fifth is daily FWMCs. Annual trends were not analyzed for TKN. The percent change over 21 years relative to the initial values is shown by the length of the bar, and the statistical significance of the trend analysis is shown by dots within the bar: none, not significant; •, p<.05; ••, p<.01; •••, p<.0001.

These analyses show that average discharge has increased in the Maumee River. Very major decreases have occurred in SRP concentrations, and substantial decreases have occurred in SS, TP, and TKN concentrations. Substantial increases in NO₃ concentrations have also occurred.

While most analyses suggested comparable amounts of change for a given parameter, the level of statistical significance was generally highest for daily data, and lowest for annual and storm event data. We were somewhat surprised that daily data performed the best, because of its tremendous variability. However, the use of log transformations and the use of flow and seasonality (months) as covariates substantially reduce this variability, and the large number of observations lend statistical strength. Apparently, the benefit of reduced variability afforded by averaging data over monthly or larger time scales is outweighed by the loss of degrees of freedom which results from the averaging process.

Figure 8. Trends in nutrient and sediment concentrations in the Maumee Basin, 1975-1995. Within each group of bars, the leftmost is the trend based on annual flow-weighted mean concentrations (FWMCs), the next is storm event mean concentrations (SEMCs), the third is monthly FWMCs based on storm data only, the fourth is monthly FWMCs based on all data, and the fifth is daily FWMCs. The percent change over 21 years relative to the initial values is shown by the length of the bar, and the statistical significance of the trend analysis is shown by dots within the bar: none, not significant; •, p<.10; ••, p<.01; •••, p<.0001.

The relatively poor performance of storm event measures was unexpected, since many BMPs are designed specifically to stop erosion during storm runoff. Analysis of the trends in data partitioned into three ranges by flow showed that, for parameters for which the overall trend is downward, the greatest change occurs during the low flow periods, and the smallest during high flow periods. NO₃ shows upward trends in the high and medium flow ranges, but downward trend in the low flow range. Flows in the highest range themselves show a downward trend, those in the middle range show no trend, and those in the lowest range show an upward trend.

Similarly, flows during the first storm runoff event in a group of closely spaced events have a downward trend, while flows in the later events in a cluster have an upward trend.

One reasonable interpretation of these results is that infiltration has increased, and overland flow has decreased. Conservation tillage is at least partly responsible for this change. Trends in concentrations at different flow regimes suggest that changes in nutrient use patterns and management practices which target erosion have both contributed to improvements in water quality. The largest *percent* changes are typically associated with low flows, when erosion is not an active process. However, since concentrations and especially loads are usually higher under high flow conditions, the largest *absolute* changes are associated with storm runoff.

Lessons Learned

- Management programs sometimes succeed in ways other than planned. No-till was initially intended as a corn practice, but most of its implementation in the Lake Erie basin has been with soybeans.
- Substantial water quality improvements can be accomplished at a large watershed scale by a mosaic of agricultural management programs, even if optimal targeting is not practiced and a single oversight agency is lacking. However, 10-20 years may be required before sufficient change occurs to be statistically significant.
- Water quality improvements need not come at the expense of lowered crop yields.
- Water quality improvements can be readily documented given appropriate statistical approaches and detailed monitoring data over a long enough period of time.
- At least for this study area, storm event concentrations and loads are less efficient metrics for revealing trends than traditional daily observations. Stratification of the data by flow showed that decreases, in percentage terms, were generally greater at lower flows, but were greater in absolute terms at higher flows.

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